

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN 21st CENTURY OF INDIA

Souvik Paul

Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Education, Raiganj University, Raiganj, Uttar Dinajpur, West Bengal, India

Dr. Biswajit Chatterjee

Assistant Professor, Department of Education, Raiganj University, Raiganj, Uttar Dinajpur, West Bengal, India

ABSTRACT

Inclusive education is a new approach towards educating the children with disability and learning difficulties with that of normal ones within the same roof. Inclusive education is a universal phenomenon extensively advocated in the recent past and as a fundamental way towards the development of Education for All (EFA) and lifelong learning. India has led in the endeavor in various programmes and media exposures which foster the integration, and more latterly inclusion of students with special needs into the main stream education system, to assess the challenges and teachers' role in inclusive education. The present study has undertaken to analyse the impact of inclusive education on the reflection of contemporary of Indian education and the role of media in inclusive education. Qualitative information has been used in this study. Data is collected on the basis of secondary sources only. It is found that Inclusion is an educational practice whereby students with special needs are fully integrated into the general education classrooms at a school. It can be stated in the conclusion of this study has come to refer to a philosophy of education that promotes the mainstream education for all pupils in schools as well as a principle and practice that is based on human rights and social justice. Inclusive education has opened a new direction in the field of education.

Keywords: children with special needs, education for all, educational needs, inclusive education

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The term inclusion refers to an approach where in students with special needs spend most of their time with non-disabled students (Inclusive Education, n.d.). Inclusive classrooms might contain several students with special needs who are mainstreamed full time into the general classroom or one, or two students who spend time each day in both a special education classroom, and a general classroom (Special Education Guide, n.d.). Inclusive education is an idea in the field of education. It means that persons with disabilities or special needs can learn at school with people who do not have special needs. The goals of an inclusive education

system is to provide all students with the most appropriate learning environments and opportunities for them to the best achieve their potential (Alberta Education, 2010). Inclusive education has grown from the belief that education is a basic human right and provides the basis for a more ethical society. All learners have the right to education irrespective of their individual characteristics or problems. Inclusive education initiatives often pay special attention to groups that have missed out on educational opportunities in the past. These groups include children living in poverty, those from ethnic and linguistic minorities, girls (in some societies), children from remote areas, and those with disabilities, or other special educational needs.

India is one of the few countries in the world where the education of Children with Special Needs (CWSN) does not come under the purview of the Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD2005) (MHRD 2005, as cited in Sanjeev & Kumar, 2007). It is generally the burden of all the central ministries of social justice and empowerment whose main focus is not education but rehabilitation (Sanjeev & Kumar, 2007). All the children whether they are disabled or not have the right to education as they are the future citizens of the country. In the governing 21st century, Indian situation resources are inadequate even to provide quality mainstream schools for common children, it is unethical and unattainable to put CWSN to test, or to prove anything in a research study to live, and learn in the mainstream of school, and community (Dash, 2006). The principle of inclusive education was adopted at the “World Conference on Special Needs Education: Access and Quality”¹ and was restated at the “World Education Forum”.² The concept of inclusion is ulterior supported by the United Nation’s Standard Rules on Equalisation of amenities for person with disability proclaiming participation and equality for all. In the 21st century, the Government of India developed and tried to implement inclusive education by formulating various policies. In this present era, inclusive education has created a special bond between disabled children and without disabled.

1.2 THE EMERGENCE OF THE TERM INCLUSION

CWSN around the world were neglected till the 18th century. Encourages political reformers and leaders in medical and education to focus their attention on the educational needs of this nation of fraternity, equality, and liberty (Chadha, 2003). According to UNESCO at the UN Committee on Rights of the Child-centre for Human Rights inclusion is:

- a) A philosophy based on the belief that all people should be equal and obeyed, and valued as fundamental human rights.

¹ They agreed a dynamic new statement on the education of all disabled children, which called for inclusion to be the norm. In addition, the conference adopted a new Framework for Action (Salamanca, Spain 1994), the guiding principle of which is that ordinary schools should accommodate all children, regardless of their physical, intellectual, social, emotional, linguistic, or other conditions (UNESCO 1994).

² The World Education Forum (Dakar, Senegal 2000) involves representatives from government and education departments across the world, and adopted the Dakar Framework for Action reaffirming the commitment to achieving Education for All by the year 2015, and entrusted UNESCO with the overall responsibility of coordinating, and significant international players in this work (UNESCO 2000).

- b) An “unending set of processes” in which children and adults with disabilities have the opportunity to partake fully in all community activities bestowed to people who do not have disabilities were mandated to provide free and consonant education in Least Restrictive Environment (LRE) with non-disabled peers to the maximum extent as possible (Chakraborti-Ghosh, 2017).

The Planning Commission of India included in its plan a programme for Integrated Education (IE). The government launched the Integrated Education for Disabled Children (IEDC) scheme in December, 1974 (Chakraborti-Ghosh, 2017). Special schools segregated CWSN from the mainstream, thus developing a specific disability culture (Chadha, 2003).

1.3 RESEARCH QUESTIONS OF THE STUDY

The research questions of the present study have followed:

RQ₁. What is the impact of inclusive education in contemporary Indian education system?

RQ₂. What is the role of media to develop the inclusive education pattern in India?

1.4 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Based on the research questions, the following objectives are constructed for this study:

O₁. To know the impact of inclusive education in contemporary Indian education system.

O₂. To know the role of media to develop the inclusive education pattern in India.

1.5 METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

Keeping in view of availability of the resources and feasibility of the present research paper, this study is conducted on the basis of secondary sources of data. This study is purely theoretical based and qualitative in nature. Content analysis is done on the available documents. The investigators are collected data from different types of books, journals (including e-journals), and articles written by the great authors. The methodology of the study is also including the thoughts and writings of various authors in the stream of academics and research.

1.6 OBJECTIVES-WISE ANALYSIS

The objectives-wise analysis has done with the help of the content analysis method, which is described below:

1.6.1 Analysis of O₁: To know the impact of inclusive education in contemporary Indian education system.

RQ₁. What is the impact of inclusive education in contemporary Indian education system?

Inclusion is based on recognition of the capacities and potential of all children to develop if the environment is responsive to their needs (Rao, 2003). The term inclusive education as referring to the education of children and youth with disabilities in general education classrooms with their non-disabled peers (Peters, 2007). Inclusive education means that all students in the school become part of the school community,

regardless of their strengths, or weakness. They are included in the feeling of belonging among other students, teachers, and support staffs.

1.6.1.1 Principles of Inclusive Education

The important principles of inclusive education are:

- Sharing the responsibilities of staff working at different levels (Tyagi, 2016).
- Providing additional support to children (Desai & Pradhan, 2017).
- Development of a collaborative framework to meet the additional needs and interests of children (Kumar, Rajendrasing, & Ram, 2022).
- Implications of various types of disabilities (Mohanty & Mohanty, 2011).
- Knowledge about family and social environment of children (Lakshmi, 2018).
- Modifications in teaching-learning strategies.
- Improving teachers' professional skills (Bandyopadhyay & Dhara, 2021).

1.6.1.2 Goals of Inclusive Education

The goal of an inclusive education system is to provide all students with the most appropriate learning environments and opportunities for them to best achieve their potential. The following goals have to be taken:

- All children can also reach their full potential given opportunities, learning effective teaching, and appropriate resources (Dash, 2006).
- Programmes will be offered to meet the individual needs of each child and student within the school community.
- The programme must address the social intellectual and physical aspects of the child's development in relation to intellectual (Mohanty & Mohanty, 2011).
- The child's education plays a key role in that they are the most complete information source and have the most investment in their child's future (Kumar et al., 2022).
- All students will have equitable opportunity to be included in the typical learning environment (Alberta Education, 2010). This means educating children with special supports and service needs in including settings is the first placement option, providing the opportunity to participate in regular classrooms with same aged peers in their neighbourhood school (Singh, 2016).
- On the basis of rationality, there will be opportunities to participate in all areas of social life subject to constraints (Mohanty & Mohanty, 2011).
- Whenever possible, the student should be a partner in his/her educational programme (Bandyopadhyay & Dhara, 2021).

1.6.1.3 Challenges of Inclusive Education

Constitutional provisions with new amendments are there, stringent laws are in place, policies are in plenty, efforts of government agencies, NGOs, and other stakeholders are there as per guidelines of international agencies, but still the results of inclusion are abysmally low, even after 25 years of India preaching the Salamanca statement (Desai & Pradhan, 2017).

- *Lack of awareness:* A school having inclusive education has to face a criticism by society and has to bear the blame of neglecting their children while paying attention to disabled or different children (Kumar, Rani, & Singh, 2016).
- *Lack of experience in an inclusion setting:* Some teachers have not been exposed to special needs classrooms and this can be a disadvantage. Educators need to coordinate efforts and understand the needs of the classroom in terms of developing skills, and lesson plans (Tyagi, 2016).
- *Negative attitude of the teacher:* Teachers, like the general public, have negative views on both disabled students, and mainstreaming. Teachers have negative attitude to mainstreaming emotionally disturbed and mentally retarded students (Mohanty & Mohanty, 2011).
- *Lack of experience dealing with severe and profound disabilities:* Students with severe and profound disabilities require more adaptation, and medical attention than the average students (Dash, 2006). Teachers must be skilled in handling severe disabilities and create lesson plans based on individual abilities, and adhere to dietary needs of the child (Bandyopadhyay & Dhara, 2021). Lack of experience can lead to the child not progressing with skills or cause of adverse medical incidents.
- *Appropriate environment:* Most schools do not have the environment to make CWSN feel welcome. There is lack of resources and infrastructures.
- *Teaching compassion of students:* Not all students have been exposed to persons with special needs and this becomes a challenge to teachers (Kumar et al., 2016). Teachers must not tolerate insensitiveness and cruelty, and teach that all students are to be treated with respect, regardless of ability.
- *Lack of attention to individual development:* The current education system does not allow for individual development of children at their own pace. Teachers are unable to cope with differences in children (Rao, 2003).
- *Lack of training:* Teachers cannot identify and work with children who are different not because they don't want to, but due to lack of training (Mohanty & Mohanty, 2011). This makes CWSN vulnerable, particularly in the Indian milieu. The teachers don't know how to deal with these children (Bandyopadhyay & Dhara, 2021).
- *Individualised lesson plans:* Because they are varying abilities in the classroom; teachers can be challenged to address individual academic needs based on ability.
- *Large classroom size:* In a typical Indian class of fifty children, CWSN, fall outside the teacher's tolerance level (Rao, 2003).

- *Non-acceptance*: Their nondisabled peers don't accept these students due to their inability and slowness to participate in normal activities (Dash, 2006).
- *Inclusive education should start from pre-school institutions*: Children are locked up home until the age of 6 and then are taken to school (Mohanty & Mohanty, 2011). They are experiencing certain psychological problems, stress; the integration process is quite difficult for them.

1.6.1.4 Role of Teachers in Inclusive Education of India

The roles of teachers in inclusive education are:

- Identification of the children with disabilities in the classroom.
- Referring the identified to the experts for further examination and treatment (Tyagi, 2016).
- Accepting the children with disabilities.
- Developing positive attitude between normal and disabled children (Bandyopadhyay & Dhara, 2021).
- Placing the children in the classroom in proper places so that they feel comfortable and are benefited by the classroom interaction (Singh, 2016).
- Removing architectural barriers wherever possible so that children with disabilities move independently (Kumar et al., 2022).
- Involving the children with disabilities in almost all the activities of the classroom (Tyagi, 2016).
- Making suitable adaptation in the curriculum transaction so that the children with disabilities learn according to their ability (Bandyopadhyay & Dhara, 2021).
- Preparations of teaching aids or adaptation of teaching aids which is help the children with disabilities learn (Bandyopadhyay & Dhara, 2021).
- Collaborating with medical and psychological panels, social works, parents, and special teachers (Kumar et al., 2022).

1.6.2 Analysis of O₂: To know the role of media to develop the inclusive education pattern in India.

RQ₂. What is the role of media to develop the inclusive education pattern in India?

The media in Indian society has taken steps to ameliorate inclusion practices and acceptance of individuals with disabilities (Chakraborti-Ghosh, 2017), like a neoteric bollywood movie "Tare Zameen Paar: Every Child is Special (2007)" hit block buster accosting dyslexia as part of learning disabilities. The movie made a sincere exertion in describing the needs and characteristics of a young boy who vied throughout his early elementary grades with dyslexia. The message was very well delivered. In the process of convincing the audience, the director Amir Khan made allusions of several renowned people who had dyslexia including Leonardo Da Vinci, Thomas Alva Edison, Alexander Graham Bell, Winston Churchill, Keanu Reeves, Albert Einstein, and last but not least popular hot bollywood star Abhishek Bachhan (Dubey, 2001).

Movies such as 15 Park Avenue (addressed schizophrenia) on severe emotional disabilities issues and services were released, and awarded by film industries, but still there is no sign of inclusion of these children

in public, or private schools (Chakraborty-Ghosh, 2017). A reality show “Sa Re Ga Ma Pa” hosted by Zee TV (www.zeetv.com) raised several gifted and talented musician with disabilities such as visual impairment, autism, multiple disabilities etc. (Sane, 2008), and another TV show “Aap Ki Antara” produced by Zee TV (www.zeetv.com) has addressed the challenges of societal unacceptance of an autistic child (Sekhri, 2009), the Indian media has helped set the stage for acceptance among Indian audiences, and it is imperative for schools to not only mirror this progress, but to prepare all children for their roles on the inclusive stage.

The Government of India has constructed various managements around inclusive education programmes in present time. These are:

- The UNESCO Salamanca Statement (1994) calls for inclusive education, stating that regular schools with inclusive orientation are the most effective means of combating discriminatory attitudes, creating welcoming communities, building an inclusive society, and achieving “Education for All” (UNESCO, 1994). Salamanca framework for action, article no. 53 stated that “The success of the inclusive depends considerably on early identification, assessment, and stimulation of the very young child with special educational needs” (Rao, 2003, p. 2).
- The National Policy on Education, 1986 recommended a goal to integrate the handicapped within the general community, at all levels as equal partners to prepare them for normal growth (Desai & Pradhan, 2017).
- In the 6th five year plan (1980-85), government considered education of children with disabilities as a priority (Desai & Pradhan, 2017).
- Government of India implemented District Primary Education Programme (DPEP) in 1994-95 which laid special emphasis on children with mild and moderate disabilities, and the DPEP was another major step towards universalisation of primary education where in CWSN are also included (Chadha, 2003).
- Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) was urged to ascertain the objective of Universalisation of Elementary Education (UEE) in 2001, is one such activity. Three exigent part of UEE are access, inscription, and accomplishment of all children in 6-14 years old. A zero exclusion approach has been permeated under SSA, which guarantees that each CWSN, independent of the kind, class, and level of incapacity, is given important quality education (Sanjeev & Kumar, 2007).
- National Curriculum Framework (NCF, 2005) has set out an unconcealed setting of inclusive education (NCF 2005). The Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD, 2005) executed a national action plan for the establishment in education of youngsters, and youth with disabilities (MHRD 2005, as cited in Sanjeev & Kumar, 2007).
- IEDC, 1974 was updated and named Inclusive Education for Disabled at Secondary Stage (IEDSS) in 2009-10 to give help to the inclusive education of the disabled children of 9th and 10th classes (Singh, 2016).
- Rashtriya Madhyamik Shiksha Abhiyan (RMSA, 2009) obligatory to incorporate these kids into coherent schools to help them conjoined and congregates their certainty (Singh, 2016).

- National Policy for Persons with Disabilities (2006) prepared by Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment recognises that persons with disabilities are valuable human resource for the country, and seeks to create an environment that provides them equal opportunities, protection of their rights, and full participation in society (Singh, 2016).

1.7 RECOMMENDATIONS AND SUGGESTIONS OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

Some of the steps that can be taken for inclusive education. These are:

- In India, the government and NGOs are initiating measures to review, and plan appropriate strategies for CWSN and inclusive education. These measures include evolving policy guidelines, analysing practices, developing teacher-training programmes, and creating resource persons and special teachers by establishing linkages to complement each other (Kumar et al., 2016).
- NCF (2005) for School Education has recommended inclusive schools for learners with special educational needs by making appropriate modifications in the content, presentation, and transaction strategies, preparing teachers, and developing learning friendly evaluation procedures (Dash, 2006).
- Teachers' attitude towards inclusive education could be formed and developed in the context of an educational system which can provide some specific conditions in order to have a good practice in this field (Rao, 2003).
- CWSN can be part of mainstream education with early intervention. If a child's specific learning difficulty can be detected by class III, then with right support of teacher, the child can overcome the difficulty by the time he reaches middle schools (Singh, 2016). Therefore, training for teachers at pre-primary and primary levels is the most important. In fact, such training should be given to student-teachers at the pre-service level. So, that they are trained to cater to CWSN when they join the schools as a teacher (Kumar et al., 2016).
- Those working in the field of education feel those teacher-training programmes at all levels M.Ed., B.Ed., and D.El.Ed. require a complete overhaul. Teachers need to be sensitised and equipped to help students with different needs, any innovation in teaching will benefit all learners (Desai & Pradhan, 2017).
- We look the other way, other country's of the principals (Head of the Institutions), from other countries of the world, expressed a positive attitude towards inclusive education. Principals with knowledge of special education showed high positive attitude towards inclusion than those without prior knowledge (Dash, 2006).
- Reducing students' exclusion from schools and focusing their increase participation in the culture, curricula, and communities of local schools (Rao, 2003).
- To respond to the diversity of students in the locality, there is a need for restructuring the culture, policies, and practices in schools (Sanjeev & Kumar, 2007).
- Reducing barriers to learning and participation for all students in the schools. Especially those who are categorised as having special educational needs.

- Learning from attempts to overcome barriers to the access and participation of particular students to make changes for the benefit of students more widely (Desai & Pradhan, 2017).
- Appropriate monitoring and evaluation mechanisms need to be put in place to evaluate the impact of inclusive education policies.
- A coordinated action plan of holistic approach is needed to bring out a change in the entire education system (Dash, 2006).
- Differently able children should be treated equally as the normal children and instead of looking them in sympathy their talents and abilities should be recognised for their self respect and welfare of the society (Sanjeev & Kumar, 2007).
- Viewing the difference between students as resources to support learning, rather than as problems to be overcome (Bandyopadhyay & Dhara, 2021).
- Emphasising the role of schools in building community and developing values, as well as in increasing achievements (Kumar et al., 2016).
- Allow flexible use of funds to support activities for inclusive schools, education, and training programmes.
- Recognising that inclusion in education is one respect of inclusion in society (Singh, 2016).

1.8 CONCLUSION

According to official estimates from the Census of India (Government of India, 2011), the number of people with disabilities in the country is 26 million, or roughly 2.1% of the total population. Successful inclusive education requires school transformation and systems change. However, much of this reform is design-focused, and not resource-intensive (Dash, 2006). It is important to emphasise that inclusive education means that all children are together in mainstream classrooms for the majority of their day (Desai & Pradhan, 2017). Inclusive education needs a set of conditions necessary to promote inclusive practice. Inclusion is essential for the growth of a person and it starts from his/her childhood, community provides adequate resources for inclusion of the individual (Sane, 2008). It is important to remember that inclusive education is at a very early stage of conceptualisation and implementation in India. The fact that is being discussed, debated, and in some places implemented although falteringly, demonstrates a willingness to engage with elements of a new concept that has the potential to be developed in the future in a positive manner (Kumar, et al, 2016). Without education, all different children may not be able to fulfil their rights as a citizen in the largest democracy of the world (Bandyopadhyay & Dhara, 2021). Therefore, providing inclusion the qualities of self confidence, self esteem, and strength of body, mind, and heart are nourished to meet such challenges. Inclusion is felt essential for success of life and any exclusion is damaging for children's development (Mohanty & Mohanty, 2011).

REFERENCES

- Bandyopadhyay, S., & Dhara, S. (2021). Teachers' attitude towards inclusive education: A literature review. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Studies*, 3(1), 214-218.
- Census of India. (2011). Government of India. Retrieved July 12, 2022 from <http://censusindia.gov.in/>
- Chadha, A. (2003). Perspectives in special needs education in India: A journey from isolation to inclusion. Retrieved September 22, 2022 from <http://www.un.org.in/Janshala/Janmar03/inclusion.htm>
- Chakraborti-Ghosh, S. (2017). Inclusive education in India: A developmental milestone from segregation to inclusion. *Journal of Educational System*, 1(1), 53-62.
- Dash, N. (2006). *Inclusive education*. New Delhi, India: Atlantic Publication.
- Desai, A., & Pradhan, D. (2017). Challenges, problems, and constraints for inclusive education: Indian context. *Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies*, 4(32), 113-119.
- Dubey, B. (2001). *Khan I do it, sir?* Calcutta times, December 2007.
- Government of Alberta: Education. (2010). Setting the direction framework: Government of Alberta response. Education and State-Alberta. Canada, North America: Alberta Cataloguing in Publication Data.
- Inclusive Education. (n.d.). *Wikipedia*. Retrieved December 15, 2022 from http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Inclusion_Education
- Kumar, S., Rajendrasing, P.V., & Ram, S.T. (2022). Inclusive education in India: Challenges and issues. *Neuro Quantology*, 20(8), 3372-3380.
- Kumar, S., Rani, K., & Singh, G.P. (2016). Inclusive education: Obstacles & suggestion in Indian context. *Bhartiya Bhasha, Shiksha, Sahitya Evam Shodh*, 7(10), 18. doi:10.32804/BBSES
- Lakshmi, R. (2018). Inclusive education in India: Challenges and prospects. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Engineering & Multidisciplinary Physical Sciences*, 6(5), 38-41.
- Mohanty, J., & Mohanty, S. (2011). *Inclusive education: Its evolutionary growth*. New Delhi, India: Deep & Deep Publications Pvt. Ltd.
- NCF. (2005). National Curriculum Framework. New Delhi, India: NCERT.
- Peters, S.J. (2007). Education for all: A historical analysis of international inclusive education policy and individuals with disabilities. *Journal of Disability Policy Studies*, 18, 98-108.
- Rao, V.H.P. (2003). *Inclusive early childhood special education (vol.16, pp.3-7)*. Secunderabad, India: NIMH News Letter.
- Sane, N. (Executive producer). (2008). *Sa re ga ma pa l'il champs*. A production of zee tv. India: ZEE TV.

- Sanjeev, K., & Kumar, K. (2007). Inclusive education in India. *Electronic Journal for Inclusive Education*, 2(2), 1.
- Sekhri, M. (Producer). (2009). *Aapki Antara*. A production of zee tv. India: ZEE TV.
- Singh, J. D. (2016). Inclusive education in India- concept need and challenges. *Scholarly Research Journal for Humanity, Science & English Language*, 3(13), 3222-3232.
- Special Education Guide. (n.d.). *Wikipedia*. Retrieved December 15, 2022 from <http://www.specialeducationguide.com/pre-k-12/inclusion>
- Tyagi, G. (2016). Role of teacher in inclusive education. *International Journal of Education and Applied Research*, 6(1), 115-116.
- UNESCO. (2000). Dakar framework for action. Paris, France: UNESCO. Retrieved October 15, 2022 from http://www.unesco.org/education/efa/ed_for_all/dakfram_eng.shtml
- UNESCO. (1994). Salamanca statement. Paris, France: UNESCO. Retrieved October 20 from 2022 http://portal.unesco.org/education/en/ev.php URL_ID =10379&URL_DO =DO TOPIC& URL_SECTION=201.html